

TRADITIONAL AND UNCONVENTIONAL METHODS

F.B.Irisboyev, D.S.Qayumov

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute.
Uzbekistan.

Explaining to students the traditional methods of obtaining energy the most used are thermal power plants (I.E.S.). Heat power plants, according to their composition, gas, coal and oil products power plants and uranium cores nuclear power plants (NPP) operating on the basis of split heat includes. The operation of power plants of the first type is fuel depletion of reserves and the impact of combustion products on the environment is limited to Raw materials in the operation of nuclear power plants resource is almost unlimited.

Chemical sources, Hydro-electric stations, Solar batteries Wind generators. Explaining to students the traditional methods of obtaining energy the most used are thermal power plants (I.E.S.). Heat power plants, according to their composition, gas, coal and oil products power plants and uranium cores nuclear power plants (NPP) operating on the basis of split heat includes[1]. The operation of power plants of the first type is fuel depletion of reserves and the impact of combustion products on the environment is limited to Raw materials in the operation of nuclear power plants resource is almost unlimited. But it is related to the use of nuclear power plants there are the following problems:

1. Rapid failure of reactor materials under the influence of radiation and release of radioactive substances.
2. The problem of radioactive waste storage.
3. Creation of a perfect safety system in nuclear reactors difficulty.
4. Working in fast neutrons, which are widely used today for gathering a large amount of plutonium in breeders and for an atomic bomb pluton, the main raw material, into the hands of ill-intentioned people the possibility of falling[3].

Today, Mike is at the University of Texas, USA The team of researchers led by Kotschenreiter is a hybrid created a synthesis-decomposition device. In the center based on the presence of a neutron source and a fusion reaction The operating CFNC (Compact Fusion Neutron Source) reactor is light water transuranium emitted from conventional NPPs operating with works with waste.

Unconventional methods of obtaining electricity to students raw materials for energy resources when explaining with unlimited, ecological purity and regeneration

different from traditional methods. Among these methods, the most recent years well studied and widely used Solar panels and electricity generation with the help of wind generators was launched. Much work has been done in this field in Uzbekistan. For example, the Sun in the Solar Physics Scientific Production Association production of batteries is underway. Uzbekistan wind generators from Denmark at the initiative of the Ministry of Energy It is being installed in Bekobad district of Fergana region. One of the promising non-traditional methods for our Republic is bioenergy. Currently, it is intended for obtaining biogas many projects of devices have been developed. These devices two tasks at once, obtaining biogas fuel and high-quality humus fertilizer carries out production. Different types of gases in the use of geothermal, volcanic energy to solve some environmental issues related to its separation it will be necessary[5].

Use of rising sea water and wave energy efficient devices developed and small power consumers is being successfully used to provide. How natural and ecological are the methods of obtaining non-conventional energy whether it is appropriate in terms of the need for energy may not fully satisfy. Therefore, the atom as the main energy of the future energy is being considered. The first to use atomic energy method about the energy of uranium nuclear fission and its problems it was mentioned above. The second method of using nuclear energy is thermonuclear is the energy of synthesis. They have been working on this for about 70 years controlled thermonuclear fusion is still in progress failed. Heat resistance is the main problem here creating new materials, strong homogeneous magnetic fields and high to present the issues of creating high-temperature refractory materials possible This information is on the topics mentioned above along with increasing students' interest in science when it is explained be careful with nature, prevent ecological damage formed the concepts of getting[2].

Chemical as one of the directions of future scientific research the issue of converting energy directly into electricity is being considered. In this case, burn differently from galvanic elements it is planned to convert oxidation energy into electricity For example, the "Apollo" spacecraft, which brought US astronauts to the moon In a hydrogen fuel cell on board, hydrogen breaks down into electricity energy and clean water. But here it is platinum as a catalyst because chemical processes have slowed down used. This causes the cost of the fuel device to be very high will come[4].

Nowadays, with the help of nanotechnology, this is the case catalysts are produced in laboratories. This is the industry hydrogen energy on a large scale creates opportunities for use. Chemical energy directly into mechanical energy In terms of

conversion, man lags far behind nature. An example of this muscle energy can be used as an example. Analyzes are muscle engine is much more useful than any machine ever created has the coefficient But until now, scientists have the mechanism of fiber contraction has not been fully studied[6-7].

These concepts are used in the teaching of physical science in students goal of knowledge formation. The above analysis on the basis of solving the energy problem facing humanity today in turn, it is necessary to perform the following tasks comes out.

1. Fuel used in traditional methods of obtaining energy economical use of resources.
2. Environmental and safety issues related to energy production solve.
3. Development of non-traditional methods of obtaining energy and to create effective technologies
4. It will be the main source of energy in the future to create controlled fusion technology
5. Chemical energy is directly electrical or mechanical to carry out scientific research on energy conversion methods[8-9].

REFERENCES

1. Irisboyev, f. (2022). elektr signallar kuchaytirgichlari va ularning asosiy parametrlari va tavsiflari. *евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(11), 190-193.
2. Irisboyev, f. b., & Mukhtorov, d. n. u. (2024). possibilities of low-energy ion implantation in obtaining nanomaterials. *oriental renaissance: innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 4(2), 122-125.
3. Irisboyev, f. b., & Mukhtorov, d. n. u. (2024). technology of manufacturing of solar elements. *oriental renaissance: innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 4(2), 107-110.
4. Irisboyev, f. (2024). the importance of energy use in the development of society. *modern science and research*, 3(1), 78-81.
5. Irisboyev, f. (2024). the place of nanotechnology in the present time. *modern science and research*, 3(1), 52-56.
6. Irisboyev, f. (2024). types and structure of synchronous machines. *modern science and research*, 3(1), 48-51.
1. 4. Metinqulov, jt (2024). atmel atmega48, atmel atmega88 va atmel atmega168 mikronatrollerlarni taqshish. *zamonaviy fan va tadqiqotlar* , 3 (1), 61-67.
2. 5. Metinqulov, jt (2024). mikroprotssessori kp580vm80a ishlash prinsipi. *nauchnyy fokus* , 1 (9), 29-32.

7. Метинкулов, Ж. (2023). использование микроконтроллеров для управления напряжением. scientific approach to the modern education system, 2(20), 149-156.